

Disciplinary Commons in TCS Portfolio

Middlesex University, London

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1 Context

1.1 University

Middlesex University is a single campus University located in Hendon, London. Modules are taught both at the Hendon campus and at overseas campuses in Mauritius and Dubai.

Middlesex University has four academic faculties:

- Faculty of Arts and Creative Industries
- Faculty of Business and Law
- Faculty of Health, Social Care and Education
- Faculty of Science and Technology

Each of the faculties has several departments. The module described here is offered by the Department of Computer Science, which is contained within the Faculty of Science and Technology.

1.2 Programme

The BSc Computer Science degree at Middlesex University is three years (or four years with placement). Students take four, 24 week, 30-credit modules per year. The compulsory modules at each level are shown in Table 1. All modules at level 4 and 5 are compulsory, at level 6 only the individual project is compulsory and the other three modules are selected by students.

At level 4 students are introduced to programming using Racket (a Lisp variant) and cover Mathematics, but when students enter level 5 there is still a very wide range of ability and understanding achieved by students in these topics.

1.3 Module

Software Engineering Management and Development (CST2550) is a 24 week, compulsory, 30 credit, level 5 module on the BSc Computer Science degree at Middlesex University.

The module currently runs at both the Hendon and Mauritius campuses.

1.4 Module Structure

The first half of the module focuses on software engineering, e.g. software development life-cycle, software testing, version control. As the functional programming language taught at level 4 is not suitable for the study of algorithms and data structures, students are introduced to C++ which is then used in the study of software engineering and algorithms and data structures.

The second half of the module focuses exclusively on algorithms and data structures.

Level	Modules
Level 4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Programming • Systems and Architecture • Foundations of Computer Science • First Year Project
Level 5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Object Oriented Programming • Operating Systems and Computer Networks • Software Engineering Management and Development • Web Applications and Databases
<i>Optional placement year</i>	
Level 6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Individual Project • Three modules selected by the student

Table 1: BSc Computer Science Structure

1.5 Learning Management System

Moodle is the learning management system used by Middlesex University, and all lab tasks; lecture slides; tests and coursework tasks are made available on the modules Moodle page. Students upload their coursework to Moodle (using TurnItIn links for written work).

1.6 Student Demographics

Each year between 100 and 200 students take the module at Hendon, and approximately 50 students in Mauritius. This year is a particularly small cohort of only 81 students at Hendon, but larger than usual in Mauritius with just over 100.

The students are mostly male, and ethnicity diverse. They are also very diverse in their abilities. This year there are 20 international students taking this module at Hendon.

1.7 Teaching Staff

I have led this module for 5 years, and in its current form for 2 years.

Due to the number of students taking the module there are multiple teaching staff for this module at the Hendon campus. This year there are also multiple staff teaching the module at the Mauritius campus. Teaching staff running lectures and practical labs are all academic staff.

In the lab sessions, academic staff are assisted by Student Learning Assistants (SLAs): current students who were selected by academic staff to assist in lab sessions at levels they have already completed. They are selected based on their academic achievement and suitability to assist other students. They reduce the demand on the teaching staff when many students have issues and questions, whilst also increasing their knowledge and understanding of the subject. Normally one or two SLAs will attend each lab session for CST2550; however, this depends on how many

students take up the offer to be an SLA and whether they are available at the timetabled lab times as they will also be studying for their level 6 modules.

1.8 Constraints

Assessment is limited as the department no longer allows exams on this degree. The assessment, therefore, is coursework only, which includes in-class tests.

Due to the use of Racket in the first year, it is necessary to teach a procedural/Object Oriented programming language at the start of the module in which the source code more closely matches the operations in the compiled code in order to be useful in the study of algorithms and data structures, particularly when calculating or timing the time complexity of algorithms.

1.9 Learning and Teaching Strategy

Support for achieving the module outcomes is provided by weekly one-hour lectures and two-hour practical lab sessions.

Formal materials are introduced in the lectures, which outline key principles; concepts and considerations. The weekly lab sessions consolidate the lecture material and provide an opportunity for students to apply the material to practical problem solving tasks.

1.10 Learning Outcomes

The learning outcomes that a student who successfully completes the module is expected to have achieved, divided into knowledge and skills, are listed below.

Knowledge:

1. Have knowledge of a variety of algorithms and data structures and the impact of algorithm and data structure selection on software performance
2. Understand the concepts of time and space efficiency and how these are measured
3. Understand the software development life-cycle and methodologies and their importance in developing software

Skills:

4. Implement, analyse and compare algorithms
5. Design and implement software
6. Manage software source code using a version control system
7. Apply automated software testing techniques
8. Effectively present and communicate design concepts

1.11 Syllabus

- Algorithms and data structures: analysis of algorithms; order of growth; asymptotic notation; implementation and design of algorithms and data structures
- Software development life-cycle and methodologies: stages of the software development life-cycle; traditional and agile approaches; software design techniques
- Software engineering: source code management using version control systems; testing, debugging and profiling tools and approaches

Week	Lecture	Lab
1	Module introduction and C++ basics	Lab introduction: Unix, Emacs and C++ compiler
2	Version Control	Basic C++ programming tasks
3	Control Flow and Debugging	Version control tasks
4	Loops and Arrays	Control flow and debugging tasks
5	Functions	Loop and Array tasks
6	Pointers and Structures	Function tasks
7	Classes	Pointer tasks
8	Build automation tools	Class tasks
9	UML	Build tool tasks
10	Software testing	UML tasks
11	Software Development Life Cycle	Testing tasks
12	Templates and ADTs	SDLC tasks
13	Algorithms and data structures introduction	Templates and ADT tasks
14	Sorting	Algorithm timing and analysis tasks
15	Data Structures	Analysing divide and conquer (sorting) algorithms
16	Searching	Data structure tasks (stacks, queues and linked lists)
17	Binary Search Trees	Symbol table tasks (comparing array and linked-list implementations)
18	Hash Tables	Self balancing tree tasks
19	Heaps and Priority Queues	Hash table tasks (comparing linear probing and separate chaining)
20	Graphs and Implementations	Heap and priority queue tasks
21	Graph Algorithms	Graph concepts and comparing DFS and BFS
22	String Matching	Graph algorithm tasks (minimum spanning tree and shortest path)
23	Dynamic Programming	Coursework 2 support
24		End of year test

Table 2: Teaching Schedule

2 Content

The material has been organised in a logical order as some earlier topics are required to understand later material. For example, big- \mathcal{O} , big- Θ and big- Ω notation and time complexity analysis is covered early on as it is essential to understanding the performance differences between different algorithms and operations on data structures.

A schedule of topics covered in the lectures and labs is shown in Table 2. Topics are introduced in the lecture a week before the associated lab tasks, which was originally applied due to timetabling constraints (i.e. some labs were earlier in the week than the lecture); however, as it gave students time to digest the material from the lecture and read the suggested section of the textbook, students were better prepared for the lab tasks, so this approach was used even when the lecture was scheduled before all lab sessions.

2.1 Essential and Supplementary Topics

The first topics are very core to the study of algorithms and data structures and are essential to the understanding of the later topics, e.g. time complexity, linked-lists, trees, resizable arrays,

sorting algorithms to build up from procedural algorithms to divide and conquer algorithms and how the time-complexity of both of them are analysed (both formally and empirically by timing C++ implementations).

Then there are less core, but still useful topics such as the study of graphs and graph algorithms, which also provides example uses of queues, stacks and priority queues which are covered earlier in the module.

The later topics in the module are a selection of topics, currently: strings and dynamic programming. Which are not essential and can change from one year to the next, but give students a taste of different approaches to algorithm design, e.g. using hashes of strings for string matching or using *memoisation* to achieve efficient implementations of recursive algorithms.

2.2 Textbooks

Multiple textbooks are used on the module, but for the algorithms and data structures portion of the module the main textbook is [1].

Whilst there is limited treatment of algorithms and data structures in the programming book [2] used in the first half of the module, it doesn't go into enough detail or cover all key topics which should be covered in the study of algorithms and data structures.

A key reason for using [1] is that it covers the topics included in the module well, particularly analysis of divide and conquer algorithms using the 'Master Method', which is not covered by some other texts, e.g. [3]. Another benefit is that this book uses pseudo-code rather than giving examples in a specific programming language, which helps to emphasise the fact that the analysis is of the algorithm and not just one specific implementation of it in a given programming language.

3 Methods and Teaching Philosophy

3.1 Methods

3.1.1 Lecture

During the lectures I introduce the topics that students will get practical experience with in the following lab session. I include some background and theory and some implementations with live demonstrations. I find students stay more focused and feel more involved with live coding, especially as I involve them in the implementation process, e.g. by asking them what I should type. When it is a topic which doesn't suit coding I still ask them questions regularly to keep them involved.

The largest issue with live coding with student participation is that it takes so long, especially as I will type their mistakes to show them what will go wrong before discussing why it went wrong. This is good for their learning, but it can quickly take up the whole a one-hour lecture; therefore, I have to strike a balance between this and explaining things to them.

Lectures include 'activities' for students to complete which are normally completed in small groups and then discussed together. While students are discussing the question together I circulate and ask some of them what they are thinking which keeps students on track with the exercise and also gives me an idea of some of the solutions students have come up with. If students aren't confident enough to volunteer their ideas in the discussion I mention some of the good ideas and they often are then happy to expand on them.

3.1.2 Sorting

Sorting algorithms are introduced over two weeks, used as an intuitive and understandable problem which allows students to get an understanding of how algorithms can be designed using the same method as you would use in the real world, and how the algorithms can be compared, e.g. stable/unstable, time complexity, in-place. It also allows an introduction to more efficient divide and conquer algorithms and how their time-complexity can be calculated by solving recurrences.

One specific example is when I introduce sorting algorithms, I start by asking students if they had a hand of playing cards, how would they sort them. From the ideas students come up with this starts a discussion about some of the more fundamental sorting algorithms, e.g. insertion sort and selection sort. It also shows the students that the first step in designing an algorithm is to think about the steps they would follow to solve a problem themselves by hand.

Then we continue to investigate how the time complexity of algorithms can be estimated by timing the algorithm and doubling the input size, or calculated by summing the frequency of operations multiplied by constants representing the cost of each operation. For both of these the insertion sort algorithm is used as an example.

In the following lecture this is further expanded upon by first reviewing the elementary sorting algorithms and their properties, and then investigating divide and conquer sorting algorithms: merge sort and quick sort, how their time complexity can be calculated by solving recurrences and how they differ, e.g. stable and in-place.

3.1.3 Lab Tasks

For most topics relating to data structures I include pen-and-paper tasks where students sketch diagrams of the data structures, before and after operations, so that they fully understand the steps of the algorithms, e.g. adding some nodes to a 2-3 binary search tree.

Then I include some programming tasks which may involve implementing operations on a partially implemented data structure. I do not require them to implement all data structures from scratch as, due to the mixed level of ability, some students would not be able to implement the data structure within the allocated time.

When teaching ‘searching’ I give students code for two alternative symbol table implementations using:

- associative arrays
- a linked-list

and require them to (informally) compare the run times.

I do this to make the students aware of the possible impact of using a less suitable data structure on the run time. In this task it is not uncommon for students to assume the program has crashed/frozen when running the linked-list implementation.

The pen-and-paper tasks are very useful in both helping students to understand the details of the algorithms and data structures and also allow me to identify misunderstandings. Students’ initial understanding of the algorithm or data structure being taught is very superficial, but to use pen and paper to actually draw the steps involved they have to check the details carefully, and after repeating these steps a few times they understand how it works. From looking at their attempts I can also see if they have understood how it works and correct any misunderstandings.

3.2 Teaching Philosophy

I aim to show the students why the topic is interesting and useful which makes the material more interesting and encourages them to learn about it. For example, until they experience how slow searching can be using a linked-list, they don’t consider the implications of which data structure they use.

Including a mixture of pen-and-paper tasks, which give students a clearer understanding of how data structures are organised and the steps involved in algorithms, and practical exercises, where students implement or use algorithms and data structures to gain an understanding of how algorithms and data structures can be implemented in a programming language and utilised in programs.

The mixture of pen-and-paper and practical tasks was inspired by the types of tasks used in [3].

I keep students participating as much as possible with activities, questions and asking their input when performing live coding examples. This keeps them actively participating and thinking about the material which helps them to take in more and increases their understanding.

I apply ideas from constructive alignment when designing modules, i.e. assessments, learning outcomes and lab tasks are closely related.

4 Student Learning and Assessment

This module has four assessment components:

- in-class tests
- practical coursework 1: software design development
- practical coursework 2: algorithms and data structures
- end-of-year test

each of which is weighted at 25% of the overall module grade.

4.1 Tests

4.1.1 In-Class Tests

The in-class tests are only 10 questions with a 15 minute time limit. They include a variety of question types: multiple choice; matching and short answer, and are automatically marked.

They are included throughout the year and focus on a specific topic to ensure students don't fall behind: students revise for the test so notice gaps in their knowledge, and to help students realise things they misunderstood and correct that understanding. To allow students to learn from the tests they are available to be reviewed at the end of the week (after all classes have taken the test) with the correct answers visible.

4.1.2 End-of-year Test

The end-of-year test is more formal and is the best indicator of what students have learnt. As it is under test-conditions, students cannot cheat or work together. This kind of assessment alone is not sufficient though as students cannot spend time thinking about and solving a problem using all of the techniques learnt in such a short amount of time.

This test covers all topics of the module in a single 1-hour, online, in-class test. It includes a mixture of multiple-choice, matching and short answer questions.

4.2 Coursework

Whilst many aspects can be assessed well with tests, they are not suitable for larger tasks which combine multiple aspects on a larger and more realistic problem. Coursework tasks allow students to gain some experience of applying their knowledge to such problems.

The practical coursework tasks for this module both have a written/presentation component and a programming component. This provides an opportunity to assess students' ability to design a solution, justify choices, analyse algorithm(s) and implement the design in a programming language.

There is also a short presentation video required for each task where students demonstrate understanding of the implementation to reduce students copying code from each other or online without any understanding.

4.2.1 Coursework 1

The software design and development coursework focusses on the topics of the first half of the module: software design and development using UML diagrams, software testing, version control, etc. This is not focussed on algorithms and data structures (which is taught in the second half of the module).

4.2.2 Coursework 2

The second coursework task allows students to put together the learning about algorithms and data structures and apply it to a practical problem. They are given a scenario and required to select/design data structure(s) and algorithms to solve the programming problem. This includes justification of the selected data structure(s) and time-complexity analysis of the algorithm(s) used for the main functionality of the system.

They then have to implement the software (using some of the tools and processes learnt in the first half of the module) and write a report.

The report is important as it gives students practice of something they would otherwise be doing for the first time in the final-year project in the following year.

Example tasks used in previous years include:

- music library for an online streaming system, which will be searched frequently by artist/band name
- system to track vehicles entering and leaving a car park
- library catalogue allowing users to search for books by title

4.2.3 Evaluating Students' Understanding

For both coursework tasks there is a short video submitted where students 'demonstrate their understanding', this was included instead of vivas when the module started being used for the BSc Computer Science degree as there were almost 200 students, so spending time on vivas with each individual student was no longer practical.

However, students tend not to demonstrate any understanding in the videos regardless of their level of understanding, so this is not a good replacement for a viva. In future I am planning to include an in-class assessment to assess the level of understanding of the submitted work by requiring students to answer questions about their submission under test conditions, e.g. where they included a certain required feature or how they would change it if this requirement was changed.

4.3 Marking and Feedback

An example marking scheme for the algorithms and data structures coursework task is shown in Table 3. The majority of marks are allocated to the elements related to algorithms and data structures, e.g. selecting appropriate data structure, analysis of algorithms and implementation matching design. Fewer marks are allocated to quality of writing, software testing, etc.

Students are provided with written feedback specific to each item in the marking scheme along with their overall marks. The feedback is written to point out where the student could improve and what they did well.

Item	Marks
<i>Report</i>	
Introduction (description of the project, not the coursework task)	5
Appropriate selection of data structure	10
Analysis of data structure and algorithms	20
Conclusion	5
References (Harvard style)	5
Layout and clarity of report	5
<i>Code</i>	
Code quality (follows code guidelines and user input validation)	10
Makefile	5
Implementation matches design	15
Implementation meets requirements	15
Catch2 test code (quality and matches testing approach in report)	5

Table 3: Coursework 2 marking scheme

References

- [1] Thomas H Cormen, Charles E Leiserson, Ronald L Rivest, and Clifford Stein. *Introduction to Algorithms*. Mit Press, 3rd edition, 2009.
- [2] Cay S Horstmann. *Big C++: Late Objects*. John Wiley & Sons, 3rd edition, 2020.
- [3] Robert Sedgewick and Kevin Wayne. *Algorithms*. Addison-Wesley, 4th edition, 2011.